

Rectifying Efficiency Measures for Vascular-based Thermal Regulation

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Outline

- Background/ Motivation
- Definition of thermal and active-cooling efficiency
- Violation of efficiency bounds in active-cooling/heating
 - Under what conditions?
 - How much is the deviation?
 - Why does it occur?
- Summary / Conclusions

Background: Need for Active-cooling

Polymer Composites

Automotive

Audi Media Center: e-tron cooling

Aerospace

IEEE Spec. **56(5)** (2019)

Thermal Stability

Active-cooling in Nature

Synthetic Active-cooling

Adv. Mat. Tech. **6(11)** (2021)

Bioinspired active-cooling is an effective thermal regulation strategy.

Definition of Thermal and Cooling Efficiency

Thermodynamics:

$$\eta_{thermal} = \frac{\text{Net work done}}{\text{Heat supplied}} = \frac{W}{Q_{in}}$$

Fund. of Phy., J.Wiley (2013)

**Restriction from
Second Law of Thermodynamics**

$$0 \leq \eta_{thermal} < 1$$

First Law of Thermodynamics: $W = Q_{in} - Q_{out}$

Active-cooling:

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Heat removed by coolant}}{\text{Heat supplied by heater}}$$

$$= \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in})}{Q_{heater}}$$

Adv. Mat. Tech. 6(11) (2021)
Int. J. Ht. Ms. Tr. 115(A) (2017)

Research Questions:

- Is active-cooling efficiency restricted to the bounds of thermal efficiency or can it exceed these limits?
 ↳ Yes, it is possible to violate the limits in the context of active-cooling [Comm. Comp. Phy. **33** (2023)]

• Can the violation of these bounds be proven and quantified experimentally?

Violation of Efficiency Limits: Theoretical Possibilities

$$\underline{\eta \leq 0}$$

(Outlet temp. $T_{out} <$ Inlet temp. T_{in})

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Heat removed by coolant}}{\text{Heat supplied by heater}} = \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in})}{Q_{heater}}$$

$$\underline{\eta > 1}$$

(Heat removed $>$ heat supplied)

1. Fluid inlet $>$ ambient temperature
2. Heater confined to inlet section

1. Fluid inlet $<$ ambient temperature

Active-cooling efficiency can violate the limits of thermal efficiency when inlet is different from ambient temperature.

Experimental Test Configuration

Temporal Evolution of Temperature

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in})}{Q_{heater}}$$

$\eta < 0$

$0 < \eta < 1$

$\eta > 1$

- Inlet higher than ambient temperature can lead to $\eta < 0$, even under active cooling.
- Inlet lower than ambient temperature can lead to $\eta > 1$.

Heat Interactions at Steady-state

Steady-state Temperature Contour

Experiment

Simulation

Binary Heat Map (Experiment)

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in})}{Q_{heater}}$$

$0 < \eta < 1$

$\eta < 0$

$\eta > 1$

- Inlet higher than ambient temperature can lead to heat flow from the fluid to the material ($\eta < 0$).
- Inlet lower than ambient temperature can lead to heat flow from the atmosphere to the material ($\eta > 1$).

Evolution of Transient and Steady-state Efficiency

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in})}{Q_{heater}}$$

Temporal Evolution of η :
($T_{in} < T_{amb}$)

Temporal Evolution of η :
($T_{in} > T_{amb}$)

Efficiency Map at Steady-state

- Steady-state efficiency values show **linear decrease** in cooling efficiency with normalized fluid inlet temperature.
- The efficiency metric is **unbounded**.
- Experimentally achievable values are only limited by fluid inlet temperatures achievable in the setup.
- There is a need for an alternate **thermodynamically consistent, bounded** cooling-efficiency metric.

Summary / Future Work

- **Designed experimental configurations** to demonstrate violation in upper and lower limits of thermal efficiency in active cooling/heating.
- **Proved** experimentally that the efficiency can **exceed** the classical bounds of efficiency by **~70 %** on either side of the limits.
- **Explained the reason for the violations** through heat flow maps.
- **Future work** includes definition of a **thermodynamically consistent performance metric** that remains bounded to the classical limits.

Kumar et. al. Rectifying efficiency measures for vascular-based thermal regulation. *In Prep.* (2025).

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Questions

Backup

Alternate Performance Metrics

Coefficient of performance (COP):

$$COP = \frac{\text{Desired effect}}{\text{Work expended}}$$

$$COP_{refrigerator} = \frac{Q_{cold}}{W}$$

$$COP_{heatpump} = \frac{Q_{hot}}{W}$$

- Definition of convenience.
- No thermodynamic restrictions.
- Value can exceed unity.

Other alternatives [Comm. Comp. Phy.. 33 (2023)]:

Hot steady-state (HSS) (without cooling)

Active cooling ($T_{in} < T_{HSS}$)

$$\eta = \frac{T_{HSS} - T_{mean}}{T_{HSS} - \min[T_{in}, T_{amb}]}$$

$$\eta = 1.69 \rightarrow \eta = 0.79$$

Active heating ($T_{in} > T_{HSS}$)

$$\eta = \frac{T_{mean} - T_{HSS}}{\max[T_{in}, T_{amb}] - T_{HSS}}$$

$$\eta = -0.82 \rightarrow \eta = 0.67$$

Cold steady-state (CSS) (with cooling)

- Alternative metrics can keep efficiency values bounded between 0 and 1.
- Construction of thermodynamically consistent definitions is a non-trivial exercise.

Proposed Normalized Efficiency Metric

Active Cooling

Active Heating

Comparative Assessment: Cooling / Heating

- The proposed normalized efficiency metric is bounded.
- However, the metric is weakly sensitive to changes in inlet temperature when $T_{\text{in}} < T_{\text{amb}}$.
- The metric is therefore not an effective one for active cooling.
- Still, the definition shows that alternate, more consistent definitions can indeed be constructed.